

The impact of teamwork on Moroccan employees

L'impact du travail en équipe sur les salariés marocains

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Abstract

Nowadays most organizations use management teams at different levels in the hierarchy so as to, coordinate their business. Teams typically make decision, solve problems, coordinate tasks, and they can influence the performance of an organization. This research project seeks to examine the impact of teamwork on the performance of Moroccan employees. Adopting a quantitative survey, this study used a cross sectional survey methods using a survey questionnaire, and this contain 25 items with Likert Scale (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree and indifferent). A questionnaire was inspired from previous researches and several analyses were done in order to test the normality reliability and validity of the data. The independent variables include (effective teamwork, effective communication, trust, leadership and recognition and reward). Whereas the dependent variable that was used is employee performance. Hence, 108 questionnaires were handed out among the Moroccan employees. The research study uses regression and correlation techniques in order to analyze the impact between two variables that is Teamwork and Employee Performance. The result of the study reveals that there is a significant positive impact of the independents variables on the dependent variable. The study recommends that teamwork activities should be adapted in order to enhance the employee performance

Keywords

Employee Performance, Teamwork, communication, trust reward & recognition and leadership

Introduction :

Nowadays and with the increased of competition, leaders figure out the ultimate importance of teamwork more than ever before, teams make it easy to expand the output of individuals through collaboration. Employees who are working in teams become the standard for the organization (Alie, Beam & Carey, 1998). The reason why teams exist because there is a task that requires a group of people to work interdependently to accomplish the aspire goals. Just being in the state where there is a task of pushing a large rock up the hill. It is obvious that no individual person working alone will be successful to do it. This task requires a group of people coordinating their efforts and sacrificing all together in order to, push in the right direction to be successful, the only reason for creating a team is to accomplish a task that can't be accomplished only by team. Recent study shows that employees working within the team can produce more output as compared to individual (Jones, Richard, Paul, Sloane& peter,2007). In the opposite, the absence of teamwork and strategies can result in job failure, disappointment, low morale, and poor productivity, which undermine the organization existence. Hence, organizations should improve the concept of teamwork among their employees in order to promote productivity and creativity and enhance the performance of each employee.

Research Questions

How significant is the impact of teamwork on the performance of Moroccan employees?

How significant is the impact of effective communication on the performance of Moroccan employees?

How significant is the impact of level of trust on the performance of Moroccan employees?

How significant is the impact leadership on the performance of Moroccan employees?

How significant is the impact of recognition and reward on the performance of Moroccan employees?

Review of Literature

Teamwork and employee Performance

The impact of teamwork on employees' occupational performance has been a crucial topic of many researches done by academics and practitioners in the previous years (Jones et al, 2007). The reason behind this attention is the fact that the practical concept of teamwork has a strong influence on the performance of any organization and the employees who work in it. Recent study shows that an employee working within a team can produce more output as compared to an individual. Jones, Richard, Paul, Sloane & Peter, (2007). According to Bailey (1999) an employee team is a group of persons who are dependent in the activities they establish and in which they share responsibility for the outcomes.

H1: Effective teamwork has a significant positive impact on Employee Performance

Leadership and employee performance

In order to make the team works properly and smoothly, it requires the presence of the leadership because he ensures all members share the workload. And agreeing on the specifics of work and how they fit together to integrate individual skills. Teamwork and leadership are two sides of the same coin what bears witness to this is that both tactical objective and strategic goals of the organization are accomplished most of the time through team effort. An effective leader will motivate, guide, inspire and challenge his team to achieve greater levels of success. (Belonio, 2012). Leadership is considered primarily as an input to team and performance, focused on the importance of functional leadership in teams Day, Gronn, Salas, 2004).

H2: Leadership has a significant positive impact on Employee Performance

Communication and employee performance

Maintaining an effective communication leads the employee to boost a high productivity as well as, binding the relationship between employees. Effective communication between leaders and employees is critically important for the potential success of a company. Accomplishing the tasks as a team has many advantages which lead to shape an effective relationship among the member of the team, in the other hand, poor communication causes anxiety among employees. Gluck (2011), claimed that, business owners should inspire their employees to communicate with one another clearly, when working together in the

organization. Leaders need to put into practice strategies to improve communication that could lead to positive work consequences (Gray and Laidlaw, 2002).

H3: communication has a significant positive impact on Employee Performance

Trust and employee performance

If there is no trust between the members of the team, we wouldn't have an effective team because the concept of trust is the necessary element that shape successful teams, Members of effective teams trust each other, and they also exhibit trust in their leaders. Interpersonal trust among team members facilitates cooperation (Robbins and Judge, 2007). Trust among the team members comes when members of the teams develop the confidence in each other competence. Rodger and Mickan (2000) concluded that there is a positive relationship between the trust and team performance. (Mickan& Rodger, 2000). Cooperation of the team members can only be created when the trust comes to be most important value of the team culture.

H4: Trust has a significant positive impact on Employee Performance

Recognition and reward and employee performance

Robbins and Judge (2007) stressed that reward system should encourage cooperative efforts rather than competitive ones. They opined that promotions, pay raises and other forms of recognition should be given to individuals for how effective they are as a collaborative team member. The managers in this state should be aware to plan and seek out to implement an appropriate reward system for the employee and encourage their participation in team projects. They must also set the groups goals which are connected towards the company strategic plan, building of employee performance and fair payment methods. Doing these things would be much easier for the managers to establish their teams. According to Dunford (1992) recognition and rewards are the basics that lead to employee's performance.

H5: *recognition and reward* has a significant positive impact on Employee Performance

Research Methodology

Type of research

This research is part of a hypothetico-deductive/quantitative approach. The hypothetico-deductive approach assumes a deductive reasoning that begins with the literature review, then the construction of a theoretical framework, and the deduction of hypothesis and the empirical test of these hypotheses and the comparison of the results with the literature (Gavard-Perret, 2011).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample size of 108 respondents were received from Moroccan employees from different cities in Morocco. The survey were distributed to the Moroccan employees .Random sampling was applied. Convenience Sampling was also applied to choose respondents among employees based on their ability and willingness to answer the questionnaire

Method of Data Collection

The items used in this study contain the five points Likert Scale of strongly agree, agree, disagreed, strongly disagree and indifferent, was developed by the researcher to collect data from the respondents on various issues surrounding employees teamwork and performance.

Demographic profile of respondents

The population of this study compromises 108 of Moroccan employees. 65 of respondents are male which is (60, 2%) and 43 of respondents are female which is (39, 8%). There were more male than women in this sample.

Concerning the average age of respondents: 57, 4% of respondents were in the age group of 24-34 years while 36, 1% of the respondents are in the age group of 18-24 years. 2, 8% of the respondents are in the age group of 35-44 years and 2, 8% are in the age group of 55-64 years while 0, 9% of the respondent are in the age group of 45-54 years.

Concerning the level of study of respondents: 35,2% of respondents are bachelor degree holders and 28,7% of respondents are bac+5 degree holders and 15,7% are Bac+2 holders and 7,4% are baccalaureate holders and 2,8% are bac+8 holders while 1,9% are high school holders.

How we analyzed Data

The process followed in this study started at first hand, by distributing the questionnaire survey through google forms, we used our network to collect data and we ask the respondents to redistribute the questionnaire for what we call the snowball technique. We codified data through Microsoft excel then we analyzed it in IBM SPSS software. After that we proceed to the technique of verification of values distribution, as mentioned in many methodology books distribution of values must be checked before running multiple linear regression .to do that we used Skewness and Kurtosis for correlation analysis and Cronbach's alpha for reliability .then we proceed to principal components factor analysis and as long as we are dealing with the latent variables measured by the five point Likert scale .it was necessary to run principal component factor analysis in order to have one index that we represent all the items of each variable of our theoretical framework. Finally, we proceed to multiple linear regression in order to measure the impact and the significance of our hypothesis .the results of these measures will be presented in the following section.

Model Summary of Employee performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.543a	.511	.505	.73264	.393	64.488	4	120,140	.000	1.697

- a. Predictors : (Constant), teamwork, communication, trust, leadership and reward and recognition
- b. Dependent Variable : Employee performance

Regression coefficient “R” = .543 or 54.3% relationship exist between (I.V’s) and (D.V). The coefficient of determination “R²” = 0.511 which show that 51.1% of variation in employee performance is explained by teamwork, Communication, team trust, leadership and reward and recognition.

Results of the hypothesis test

Hypotheses	B	P	T	Conclusio n
Effective Teamwork → employee performance (H1)	.341	.00 2	3.445	Supported
Communication → employee performance (H2)	.113	.00 0	7.148	Supported
Trust → employee performance (H3)	.260	.00 0	3.395	Supported
Leadership → employee performance (H4)	.231	.00 4	3.568	Supported
Reward and recognition → employee performance(H5)	.250	.00 2	1.941	Supported

Conclusion

The independent variables teamwork, trust, Reward and recognition, Leadership and communication explained 34.1%; 26%; 25%; 23%; 11.3% of variation respectively towards dependent variable of employee performance. The overall result revealed that teamwork, communication, trust, Leadership, Reward and recognition and the dependent variables are positively correlated. this study highlight the major importance of teamwork inside every single organization and it's positive impact on the performance of Moroccan employees, which brings fruitful benefits such as higher productivity, organizational performance and competitive advantage.

Limit of the Study

It should be noted that this study was done in a short period of time and a short sample size which is 108 participants .therefore, based on the Data collected we may not generalize the results.

Future Area for Research

There are several other factors that may impact the performance of Moroccan employees and these need to be investigated further.

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